

Batteries & Supercaps

Supporting Information

Elucidating Degradation Mechanisms of Silicon-graphite Electrodes in Lithium-ion Batteries by Local Electrochemistry

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S1- EIS experiments using three-electrodes cells: T-cell and coaxial Swagelok cell

A T-cell is shown in **Figure S1(a)**, and it was used for the first trial of SEI formation. The T-cell consists of the circular anode sample as WE and a metallic lithium disk (CE, dia. 12 mm). The Si-C anode sample was separated by a polyolefin membrane and (12 dia. mm) from the classic separator made by glass fibre, which was soaked with 100 μL 1 M LiPF_6 ; EC:DMC (1:1 wt%) + 2% VC w/w as electrolyte. The use of the polyolefin membrane was a precaution to avoid damage to the SEI surface after cell disassembly. Test measurement in the absence of the polyolefin membrane showed that parts of the anode were attached to the glass fibre separator. A piece of Li was used as RE (6 mm). An additional glass fibre separator soaked with 50 μL SEI electrolyte was placed between the electrode sandwich and the side of the reference electrode to prevent short-circuiting. Global electrochemical impedance measurements were conducted with pristine Si-C electrodes and after the cycling processes. EIS were registered in 1 M LiPF_6 and EC:DMC (1:1 wt%) +2% VC (w/w) before (pristine, DC potential around 2.1 V) and after (cycled samples, DC: around 0.1 V) the cycling process (**Figure S1(b)**). The electrochemical impedance spectra presented loops in the low-frequency domain, interpreted as artefacts as described previously.^[35]

Figure S1. (a) Swagelok T-cell, (b) Nyquist plots obtained using a T-cell for a pristine Si-C sample and after cycling. Frequency range: 100 kHz to 100 Hz in 1 M LiPF_6 (EC:DMC).

The EIS evaluation was performed in a coaxial Swagelok (3 electrodes cell) to avoid artefacts and misled interpretation. **Figure S2(a)** shows the coaxial cell and **Figure S2(b)** the coaxially positioned RE in plane with the (annular) CE. The WE electrode plungers were PEEK cylinders pressed into a stainless-steel contact sleeve. In the central part, a stepped surface (dia. 2 mm) with a small bore hole (0.5 mm) was located. This bore hole in combination with a thread and a set screw serves as an extrusion hole for the metallic lithium RE described previously.^[35,32] The three-electrode cell is assembled for cycling with 80 μL electrolyte. **Figure 1(c)** in the main manuscript resumes the Nyquist plots obtained of each cycled electrode, parameters of EIS were similar to the above described.

Table S1. Data values were obtained by fitting Nyquist plots to EQC.

Cycle No.	$R_{SEI} + R_{ct}$ (Ω)
1	28.7
3	40.4
5	46.3
7	52.0
9	66.0
11	108.3

(a)**Figure S2** (a) Coaxial Swagelok cell and components. (b) Coaxial RE positioned in the middle of the CE.

S2 Coulombic efficiency

Figure S3 is representative of a measurement to calculate the Coulombic efficiency. **(a)** Shows representative cyclic voltammograms for each sample (9 cycles sample) recorded with the coaxial Swagelok cell filled with 1 M LiPF₆ (EC:DMC) + 2% w/w VC as electrolyte. The potential was cycled from OCP to 0.01 V and then further scanned from 0.01 V to 1.5 V at a scan rate of 0.1 mVs⁻¹. **Figure S3(b)** presents the current as a function of time, and **Figure S3(c)** resumes the integrated anodic and cathodic peaks (charge) of each cycle, showing that the Si-C lithium-ion intake is decreasing as the number of cycles increase. The coulombic efficiency (CE) was calculated by the ratio $\frac{Cd}{Cc} \times 100$, where Cd is the discharge capacity of the cell at a single cycle, Cc and is the charge capacity of the cell in the same cycle. **Table S2** shows the CE of each cycled electrode and the mean values.

Figure S3 (a) CV of the 9 time cycled Si-C electrode in the potential window of 1.5 to 0.01 V vs Li/Li⁺ at a scan rate 0.1 mVs⁻¹ in 1 M LiPF₆ (EC:DMC) + 2% w/w VC. (b) Plot of current (mA) vs time; (c) charge obtained for each cycle; (d) plot the % CE for all differently cycled electrodes.

Table S2. Coulombic efficiency (%) values for each cycle

No. of Cycle [a]	Mean ^[b]	SEM ^[c]
3	91	1.56
5	92	1.17
7	94	0.67
9	95	0.00
11	95	0.00

[a] Number of cycles; [b] mean of coulombic efficiency values, and [c] calculated standard error of mean for the CE.

S3 Scanning electrochemical microscopy measurements

SECM measurements were carried out using a home-built instrument installed in an Ar-filled glovebox (Jacomex) with levels of $\text{H}_2\text{O} < 0.1$ ppm and $\text{O}_2 < 0.1$ ppm. SECM measurements were conducted in a three-electrodes coaxial set-up: the working electrode (WE, SECM tip) is positioned in the middle of the cylindrical counter electrode (CE), and the reference electrode (RE) is retained at an external area of this cylindrical counter electrode, as shown in **Figure S4**. The SECM positioners and the potentiostat were controlled by an in-house programmed software. All potentials were measured against a reference electrode composed of metallic Li (ribbon 99.9%, Sigma Aldrich) inserted in a glass Pasteur pipette separated by a ceramic frit. The reference electrode reservoir was filled with 1 M LiClO_4 and EC:PC (1:1 wt%) solution to match the electrolyte in the electrochemical cell. The counter electrode was made of titanium mesh (Alfa Aesar) coated with carbon nanotubes (CNTs) using polyvinylidene difluoride (PVDF) as a binder with a 4:1 weight ratio (wt). The working electrode was a 25 μm platinum disk-shaped ultramicroelectrode. All SECM studies were performed in 1 M LiClO_4 in EC:PC (1:1 wt%) supporting electrolyte solution. EC:PC was used as electrolyte to avoid evaporation during the long-term SECM measurements in the used open cell configuration. FB-SECM experiments were carried out with the addition of 10 mM Fc (ferrocene). Si-C anode samples were used as substrate.

Figure S4. Schematic of the SECM setup inside an Ar-filled glove box

S4 SECM approach curves for determination of the electron-transfer kinetics (k)

Recorded approach curves are shown in **Figure 3** in the main article. k is the dimensionless constant of the first-order kinetics (cm/s) obtained by fitting to a mathematical function used to acquire quantitative information from the approach curves.^[33] The major parameters are the diffusion coefficient, the radius of the disk-shaped SECM tip and the RG value. The calculated radius of the tip was 12.5 μm , the RG value was 11 and the diffusion coefficient of ferrocene was $2.03 \times 10^{-6} \pm 0.2 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$.^[36] Fitting values of k are plotted in **Table S3**.

Table S3. Mean values of reaction rate (k) constant derived from SECM approach curves ($n = 7$) towards Si-C electrode samples prepared with varying cycling conditions.

No. of cycles ^[a]	k mean values (cm.s) ^[b]
pristine	4.21×10^{-2}
1	9.05×10^{-4}
3	9.09×10^{-5}
5	2.01×10^{-6}
7	2.01×10^{-6}
9	4.01×10^{-4}
11	2.68×10^{-3}

[a] Individual anode samples were were cycled with the potential scanned to 0.01 V (0 cycles but SEI formation) and then cycled between 1.5 V and 0.01 V. [b] Mean values of electron-transfer rate constant obtained from fitting the FB-SECM approach curves in presence of an outer-sphere electron transfer redox mediator (here: ferrocene).

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References

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